

**Exclusion in the Westphalian System:
Rethinking International Relations Through Heteronomous Society**

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Abstract

This study critically examines the political implications of the Westphalian system, a framework long dominating International Relations (IR) theory. Despite critiques supported by historical evidence, the system continues to serve as a conceptual foundation for understanding contemporary international society. This paper contrasts the Westphalian model with the medieval European social system to elucidate key differences. The findings reveal that modern international society is structured by three interrelated levels: the Westphalian system, sovereign states, and existentially unified subjects. These elements foster divisions of friend and enemies as theorized by Carl Schmitt, thereby giving rise to radical forms of exclusion. In contrast, medieval Europe was organized through a heteronomous social structure, states incapable of monopolizing violence, and subjects encompassing internal contradictions. Far from causing disorder or chaos, these features mitigated radical exclusion and promoted a unique form of social inclusion. The paper concludes by advocating the need to move away from the repressive and exclusive Westphalian model, calling for a re-evaluation of existing policies and proposing a heteronomous medieval society as a potential alternative based on the varied and complex nature of actors in IR.

1. Introduction

1.1. The Persistent Influence of the Westphalian System

The field of International Relations (IR) is often shadowed by the Westphalian paradigm. The Westphalian system, originating from the Treaty of Westphalia in 1648, is characterised by two significant facets: a contemporary significance that positions sovereign states as the most vital actors in analysing today's international politics and understanding international

relations through their interplay, and a historical framework that traces the origin of modern international relations to the Treaty of Westphalia, signed in 1648 after the Thirty Years' War (Yamashita et al., 2016). Throughout its history, IR has consistently used the Westphalian system as a significant theoretical foundation, especially among realists.

Notably, Hans Morgenthau, a classical IR theorist, developed realism rooted in power politics, which he saw as a manifestation of human nature and political interests, with the Westphalian system as a cornerstone (1967). The Westphalian system was also a vital theoretical base during the neo-neo debate of the 1980s, an era that brought enhanced precision to the field through a more structural perspective. For instance, Kenneth Waltz, a Neorealism theorist, portrayed the international system as anarchy, a setting where rational states prioritise self-preservation and power balance (Waltz, 1979). This perspective allowed for theoretical expansions, such as adjusting to changes in the international system's structure, like shifts in the number of major powers. Other theorists, like Robert Keohane & Joseph Nye, underlined the importance of international institutions and markets within this anarchic system, introducing a neoliberal viewpoint that emphasises interdependence—a concept realism lacks (Keohane & Nye, 1972). Both Neoliberalism and Neorealism uphold the persistent Westphalian idea of sovereign states and rational choice, leading to a theoretical convergence known as the neo-neo synthesis (Wæver, 1996).

However, the Westphalian system's simplistic view of states—also called the billiard ball model—has drawn criticism for overlooking the internal dynamics of states. A main critic, Alexander Wendt, founded constructivism, which brought a fresh sociological angle to existing IR theories (1992). By highlighting the different impacts of British and Russian missile ownership on the United States, he stressed the need for context-specific sociological scrutiny. Wendt challenged the idea of states having a fixed essence, noting actions with diverse identities on an international level, such as being leaders of the free world or imperialist states. This led to a new understanding of state actions, taking into account the state's behavioural history and acknowledging the potential for various identities. Yet, even within this critique, state relations continue to form the basic theoretical framework of IR.

Consequently, as the Westphalian system is repeatedly referenced across all IR theories, Atsushi Shibasaki argues that the history of IR has been limited to a interpretation of this system (2016, p.43). With this in mind, it can be said the vibrant debates on 'isms' in IR have

evolved based on a relatively 'peaceful' state-centric outlook, known as the Westphalian system.

1.2. Rethinking the Historical Validity

Waltz emphasises the ontological universality of the Westphalian system of realism in IR, asserting from a neorealist standpoint that 'the enduring anarchic character of international politics accounts for the striking sameness in the quality of international life through the millennia, a statement that will meet with wide assent.' (1979, p. 66). Such an atomistic and essentialist view of realism historiography either completely ignores or trivialises the qualitative differences between mediaeval and modern international system, thus flattening history by rendering it uniform.

The aforementioned historical perspective has been subject to extensive criticism. For example, John Ruggie emphasised the difference between the mediaeval European society and the modern international system, characterised by clear divisions and principles of sovereignty. He noted that the mediaeval European society consisted of various actors, such as the sacred and secular authorities, power and prestige, the pope, local lords, the knightly class, etc (Ruggie, 1993). These intermingled in a network of overlapping authorities, intertwined jurisdictions, and complex personal and territorial relationships, together forming what he termed a 'heteronomous institutional framework' (Ruggie, 1983).

Furthermore, Benno Teschke critically examined the myth of the birth of the modern international system in the Treaty of Westphalia in 1648 through a materialistic historical validation, meticulously studying the differences in the internal situations of European countries since the Middle Ages (2003). Teschke distinguished the aspects often conflated in historical examinations of IR, such as England and France, and modern states and absolutist states, by focusing on class relations, emphasising England's unique role at the beginning of the modern state system. In England, the parliamentary system was established ahead of other European countries, allowing for rational diplomatic policies, separated from the personal character of the monarch. Moreover, England abandoned territorial acquisition in Europe, shifting its policy towards balance of power and blue-water colonial policy. Other European countries were forced to reform in the face of England's growing strength, leading

to a reorganisation of domestic regimes. By focusing on England's role as the first capitalist state and its policies, Teschke reinterpreted the significance of 1648, substantially diminishing its importance compared to what has been repeatedly mentioned in traditional IR, and viewed the establishment of the modern state system as a gradual process from the 17th to the 19th centuries.

Thus, the historical validity of the Westphalian historical view has significantly declined today due to several empirical accumulations and important research concerning historical recognition.

1.3. Mythological Paradox of the Westphalian System

On the other hand, it has been pointed out that limitations exist in revisionist historical studies of the Westphalian regime (de Carvalho et al., 2011). They argue that even if critics of the Westphalian system offer more accurate historical interpretations, the field can continue as it is, unaffected by revisions of the historical context regarding the origins, evolution and changes of the regime, as long as the international community of today, which IR researchers study, conforms to the Westphalian model He argues that.

By adopting a methodology in which international relations theory refers to the Westphalian system as a premise of the discipline, the Westphalian system allows for a self-referential cycle of hypothesis and verification, even if it is detached from its historical starting point and loses its historical reality (Shibasaki, 2016). However, this situation of simultaneous construction of theory and reality creates a situation in which hypotheses can be constructed and tested without the ultimate basis of theory. The Westphalian system was, so to speak, a cyclical system without purpose that continued to reconstruct state-centrism in order to realise state-centrism. The above structure gives the Westphalian system the paradoxical status of acquiring a position as an enduring system, despite the fact that it is a product of its time.

This self-referential and obstructive IR disciplinary tendency is still persistently reflected today In a special issue of the European Journal of International Relations (EJIR) in 2013, entitled 'The end of IR?', Tim Dunn and colleagues analysed the recent IR literature (2008 - 2013), analysed the recent IR literature (2008-2013). They noted a decline in paradigm

disputes and an increase in cross-references between 'isms'. They noted that the field is in a state of 'disengaged pluralism', where scholars are free to pursue their own agendas and ignore alternative views, and where there is no traditional 'great debate'. This not only implies a stoppage of theoretical development within the field, but also a stable state in which the absoluteness of the Westphalian system as an analytical tool for international relations today is unquestioned, as the respective theories based on the Westphalian system cite each other.

Having thus fallen into a loop of hypothesis and verification without questioning its basic premises, international relations theory, as a discipline, has a relatively stable ontological basis and, at the same time, begins to have the legitimacy of being objective and scientifically valid in this closed space. What is detrimental about the Westphalian system is that this self-running state of transcending history begins to have a political norm that only practices associated with sovereign states are correct, shaping political practice beyond its position as a mere framework of perception, and shapes political action. The rise of non-state actors since the Cold War is an important trend, but one that is often overlooked in Westphalian analysis. Current issues include inequality, human rights, multiculturalism and perspectives involving international organisations, NGOs and civil society organisations. However, the Westphalian system functions as a norm in these areas and all issues are limited to its objectives and territorial setting. State-centred views prevail and the solution of non-state actors' problems is limited to the state (Shibasaki, 2016).

Thus, when the Westphalian regime forms a self-contained norm, IR creates an enduring reality in which questions about the potential of the underlying system are blocked and the focus is solely on inter-state relations. When the oppressive norms of the Westphalian regime universalise the sovereign state and make the framework self-referential, non-state actors become passive. The framework become fixed as key assumptions, and questioning these assumptions becomes a non-issue. The Westphalian system is more than a theory, it guides the construction of a new world. These features show that international relations theory continues to reproduce itself by 'building its objectives and domains' (Shibasaki, 2016, p.43). Despite vague origins, the Westphalian system maintains significant influence, forming facts from myth.

1.4. Research Questions, Objectives and Methods

In the study of IR, the Westphalian system's self-contained and self-referential framework has revealed limitations. By constantly reinforcing and verifying its hypotheses, it asserts an everlasting supremacy, leaving its normative and practical implications unquestioned. It can therefore be argued that the myth continues to dominate the field today. As such, critiques of the historical genesis of the Westphalian system and its greater or lesser explanatory capacity in understanding international relations today did not provide a corrective to the IR practices that are functioning today.

The central exploration in this paper, therefore, is to identify what kind of political practice is produced in the process by which this system continues to reconfigure itself. In doing so, it aims to identify the problems inherent in the framework, to cast doubt on its legitimacy as a framework and to facilitate a break from its domination in the field. The methodology of this research involves a historical study comparing the Westphalian system with the social structure of medieval Europe. In order to understand the medieval system, Ruggie's concept of heteronomous society will be used as an auxiliary line. This will enable to examine the differences once again, while criticising the realist view of history that ignores the dynamism from the modern to the medieval period. By examining contemporaneous philosophical and theological theories, the discussion will also be extended to how the systemic differences affected political practice and subject formation.

Finally, this study will identify the problems with the normatively functioning Westphalian system as a framework, and examine the potential of the medieval system as an alternative to overcome its limitations and to provide new guidelines.

2. The International System in Mediaeval Europe.

2.1. Realist View of the Mediaeval System

From a neorealist standpoint, Walz (1979) likened the mediaeval international system to the modern one, highlighting the persistent presence of anarchy. This presents an urgent query: how effective is this attempt to link mediaeval and modern eras through their shared essence? This section seeks to probe this matter, evaluating the realist's oversimplified

perspective on history and inspecting the disparities and continuities between mediaeval Europe and the post-modern international system.

Susan Reynolds offers a stance that coincides with the realist interpretation of mediaeval history. She contends that during the Middle Ages, a rational state with substantial control over violence existed (2003). As groundwork for her argument, Reynolds broadens the modern state's definition, as given by Max Weber, to suit a wider historical range. By employing common terminology across varying times, she strives to distinctly position each period's unique situations on a comparative basis. Reynolds' assertion emphasises the fact that the political communities she termed as states in this era never wielded sovereignty. She amends Weber's portrayal of the state as a 'monopoly of violence' to 'control of violence,' tempering this with the qualifier 'more or less.' She contends that while the Church exerted strong control over people facing eschatological fears, it lacked the coercive legitimacy characterizing other political organizations; thus, it does not qualify as a state. Conversely, she claims that most political forms present in the Middle Ages, such as kingdoms, principalities, collectives, and various types of lords, can be categorized as states.

Hence, subsequent sections will investigate the intricacies of the medieval international system to scrutinize Reynolds' assertions. Further exploration will be given to the Pope's role as an external challenger to the authority of medieval kings, as well as the internal sway of vassals within the feudal framework.

2.2 . Layered nature of the Mediaeval Ages

2.2.1. Church

Discussing the mediaeval system by comparing it to the modern concept of the 'state' likely reveals more differences than similarities, especially in IR. Most importantly, we need to dismiss the idea of structural anarchy, commonly linked with the Westphalian system. Even if some polity that existed in the Middle Ages are referred to as states, the outside of the state can never be called anarchy. There existed the Church and the Holy Roman Empire, as universal authorities and right-holders. In the Latin world, everything theoretically existed under the authority of the Pope and the Emperor, even in large dynastic monarchies to small fiefs and free cities (Lesaffer, 2004).

The practice of excommunication serves as an illustrative example of the Church's universal sway. In severe cases, it meant complete expulsion from the Christian community, with all of the Church's blessings withdrawn, including prohibitions on entering the Church or receiving a Christian burial. This measure was used against grave moral or faith-related crimes, but from the late Middle Ages, it was also applied to perjury, forgery, violence against clergy, misappropriation of church property, violations of asylum laws, and failure to appear in court, often being utilised as a technique to isolate rulers (Pavlac, 1991). Since Christianity had an enormous influence on society at the time, excommunication also had significant political implications. For example, Archbishop Bruno of Trier (1101-1124) countered the persecution of St. Maximin's Abbey through acts of violence and asset plundering by the Count of Luxembourg by excommunicating William and his son Conrad in 1122. Having received the declaration of excommunication, the count, acknowledging his misdeeds, went so far as to send a petition for the withdrawal of the excommunication to Archbishop Bruno. This incident illustrates that the archbishop's authority was not just spiritual but also exerted a significant influence in maintaining order within his jurisdiction (Gwynn, 1950).

The event where Henry IV was excommunicated and humiliated at Canossa during the end of the Investiture Controversy also underscores the far-reaching influence of the papacy. Excommunication meant expulsion from Christianity and the loss of royal authority to rule. Based on the writ of excommunication and abdication, the election of Rudolf of Rheinfelden as the new monarch by the Saxons caused no small confusion within the empire (Morrison, 1962), prompting Henry IV to go directly to Canossa to seek forgiveness.

However, it's crucial to acknowledge that the Church's authority was not so overpowering as to force compliance from all power-holders. The incident of 1077, symbolised by Bismarck's parliamentary statement "We will not go to Canossa," has been overemphasised, tied to 19th-century Prussian nationalism and as part of the German emperor's tragic historical narrative. Significant questions linger regarding the impact of Henry IV's excommunication. Pope Gregory VII refrained from explicitly supporting Rudolf, who was elected the new king after Henry's excommunication, and continued to refer to Henry IV by his kingly title even after his excommunication (in a secular sense, not as a sacred king). The views surrounding the incident of 1077 have sparked debate between Johannes Fried (2008), who understood it as the result of careful political negotiation and emphasised the secular significance, and

Ernst-Dieter Hehl (2019), who interpreted it as an ecclesiastical and liturgical rite and emphasised the sacred meaning. Limited primary sources have contributed to these divergent viewpoints. However, a consensus emerges in the rejection of portraying the incident as mere papal despotism or the emperor's defeat (Huffman, 2020). In this era where religion and politics were closely linked, the incident had enough sway to unsettle the domestic power structure, whether motivated by religious or political reasons. Yet, while excommunication did disrupt the established power hierarchy, the Pope's influence wasn't sufficient to entirely dismantle the existing political framework.

In the end, within the mediaeval European international system, political entities could "more or less" control violence as Reynolds stated, and sometimes not control it. As a result, the power of individual states was often undermined by external influences. Notably, even the Roman Pope, who was believed to possess universal authority, never held a monopoly over violence. Therefore, it would be inaccurate to assert that the conditions of this era resembled modern structural anarchy.

2.2.2. Feudalism

Moreover, the unity of the political system was often internally challenged during the mediaeval era. To understand this, it is necessary to point to the imperfections of feudal hierarchies and the complex networks that enabled multiple loyalties.

The feudal practice of land granting started to take shape in the 7th and 8th centuries, and by the 9th century, these relationships became fundamental. The mainstream view has long been that the imperial expansion during Charlemagne's rule in the 9th century relied heavily on the feudalization of the post of government official and the construction of a hierarchical system with the king at its apex to establish political order. However, some critiques, such as those by Dendorfer (2004), point out that only a small number of identifiable vassals existed within the Frankish kingdom. In Fried's study, titled "Warum es das Reich der Franken nicht gegeben hat (Why the Empire of the Franks did not exist)," he critiques an anachronistic error in recent scholarship. He notes that the Frankish kingdom, originally understood as a "Regnum" or an area under royal influence that internally comprised various ranks such as bishops and counts, is now mistakenly conceptualized as a "Reich"—indicative of a political

institution or system (2005). Moreover, the loyalty dictated by feudal relations was not an absolute priority. For instance, in mid-12th century Germany, Count Gebhard II of Sulzbach, although an important vassal who held extensive lands within the Bishopric of Bamberg, did not display consistent loyalty towards the Bishop. His allegiance shifted in 1132 when his relative became the Bishop of Regensburg, weakening his relationship with the Bishop of Bamberg (Dendorfer, 2004). In this context, even though feudal bonds were formally established through the granting of fiefs and contracts, other social practices of the time, such as familial ties and friendships, often played an equally, if not more, significant role in dictating loyalty and behavior.

Furthermore, the concept of multiple vassalage introduced a new dynamic to feudalism. What this concept illustrates is that feudal relationships were not confined to a simplified one-to-one contract between a vassal and a lord, but an expansive system of governance where a single vassal could be in feudal relationships with multiple lords. The origin of this phenomenon has been a subject of intense debate among historians, with Georg Waitz attributing it to the early 9th century, while François-Louis Ganshof places it in the latter half. Recent approaches, such as that of Deutinger (2002), identify a document created in the French town of Angers in 1037 as the oldest clear evidence. Even after the emergence of these multiple loyalties, there were those who swore loyalty to a single monarch, such as William of Évreux in the first half of the 12th century, but such cases became exceedingly exceptional. The system of multiple vassalage continued to expand and spread, taking root in Germany by the mid-11th century and extending to various countries such as southern Italy, England, and Barcelona in the latter half. By the 12th century, multiple vassalage had become a common institution throughout Europe (Ganshof, 1961, p.192). As a typical example, the feudal records concerning Count Siboto von Falkenstein of Bavaria demonstrate that he was a vassal to 19 different monarchs.

Swearing loyalty to multiple lords simultaneously meant contradictions between each loyalty, negating the realist vision of a singularly converging domestic order between the lord and vassal. From such characteristics, some studies have portrayed multiple vassalage as "véritable lèpre de la vassalité (a veritable leprosy of vassalage)" (Bloch, 1982, p.211), depicting it as something that caused the collapse of the reciprocal relationship between subjects and monarch, and even the collapse of feudalism itself. However, recent research

has essentially revised this understanding, positioning multiple vassalage not as indicative of the decay or dysfunction of feudalism. For the vassal, having multiple lords was utilised as a legitimate and rational means of expanding territorial control, not a product of chaotic loyalty but something that emerged within the unique context of feudalism. In cases where the contradictions of multiple vassalage were most pronounced, such as conflicts between serving lords, legal resolutions were possible through predetermined priorities or exclusion clauses. Alternatively, a vassal might maintain neutrality towards both sides, providing money or shared military forces, or situations might arise where knights split themselves into two factions and fought amongst themselves (Terada, 2006). This can be understood as reflecting the positive aspect inherent in the flexibility of feudalism, where vassals could act freely without being bound to a state, rather than appearing as a harbinger of the collapse of feudalism based on the lord's absolute power (Peters, 2020).

In the governance of mediaeval Europe, the concepts of monarch's clear hierarchy and unity were tested on multiple fronts. It can be concluded that the monarch's influence was perpetually restricted - externally by the Christian faith's overarching sway and internally by the demands and constraints of the feudal vassals themselves.

2.2.3. Plurality of Government

The above has examined whether a state of the kind Reynolds describes existed in mediaeval society from both sacred and secular, inside and outside. Reynolds tried to classify mediaeval kingdoms, countships, etc., into the category of states by replacing Weber's definition of the 'monopoly' of violence with the word 'control' and further diluting it with the phrase 'more or less.' However, if we are to acknowledge the existence of states in the mediaeval sense as Reynolds does, it can be said that this explains only one aspect of mediaeval European society with its multifaceted nature. In mediaeval society, state control was only one aspect of the multi-layered governance relationships that existed, and violence was more or less controlled by other authorities. To recognize the existence of states in the Middle Ages in IR theory, by giving the state endless elasticity (Davies, 2003) through the extension of its definition, the systemic differences mentioned above would become invisible.

Ultimately, we may return to Ruggie's portrayal of mediaeval society as diverse and multifarious. Unlike the Westphalian system, mediaeval society consisted of a “patchwork” (Strayer, 1959, p,115) of overlapping and incomplete rights of government, forming layers within the social fabric. To grasp the characteristics of today's international system, focusing on the differences from the mediaeval model may prove more enlightening than trying to force commonality through the term 'state'.

As understood from Machiavelli's "The Prince" by Foucault, a monarch's governance during Middle era was merely one specific practice among the many practices of governance that existed in society. Inside the state, in a political sense, there were many other practices of governance, including those by family fathers, abbots of monasteries, teachers, and even children or disciples. Machiavelli's concern was about who governed, to what degree, for what goal, and by what means a nuanced perspective that considered different internal and external forces (Foucault, 2007). In medieval society, states never achieved a stable, sovereign status; instead, they were part of a complex, overlapping layer of exclusive and non-exclusive authorities without clear boundaries. This plurality of governance in the medieval setting contrasts with today's sovereign states, which are characterized by a single form of legitimacy. Governance systems that were inherently contradictory coexisted in a non-exclusive manner within the same geographical space, influencing politics through their relative relationships. This led to a domestic political landscape marked by incommensurable and multilayered coexisting authorities and practices.

2.3. Mediaeval System, Subjects and Contradictions

The shift from the mediaeval system to the modern one resonates strongly with the Enlightenment theory articulated by Max Horkheimer and Theodor Adorno. They identify modernity, marked by rationalism and empiricism, as a framework driven by a consistent space of formal argumentation (2002). During the mythical age, objects held spiritual essence and symbolism. For example, a tree was not just a physical entity but bore sacred significance, embodying spiritual energy (mana) that was fluid and changeable rather than static. Contrastingly, in the modern era, only those concepts that fit within a self-converging theoretical unity are given a fixed existence or considered an event. Meanings or existences

that do not conform to this unifying principle are excluded in a restrictive manner. By adhering to a sole governing force, the truth of the world aligns with the power that mandates this compliance, and the world's elements are restricted to an order defined by that authority. Thus, within the uniform space defined by modern Enlightenment, reality is validated, its continuity confirmed, its concept crystallised, and its intricate variations dismissed. This unity emerges from an atomistic comprehension that carries an unvarying essence.

By substituting 'Enlightenment' with 'sovereign state,' we can discern that the modernization of the international system reflects the same transition. In the mediaeval framework, the overlapping of multiple governments resulted in a lack of clear affiliation and internal unity. The inability to monopolize violence inherently led to a non-monopolistic stance on truth as well. In contrast, modern sovereign states have negated internal plurality and diversity by monopolizing violence, thereby compelling obedience to a singular authority. Foucault identified the existence of biopower as a new form of power in modernity. Unlike traditional power, which focused mainly on the authority to kill or let live, this innovative power encompassed aspects of production and health, grasping and managing life itself (Foucault, 1995). Such life-controlling power that normalises all aspects of existence became theoretically possible only through a fundamental shift from the mediaeval international system. This was because the existence of multiple governments in mediaeval society created a state where people within the system were influenced by several different powers simultaneously. This negated the concept of monopolistic and exclusive domination over life, rendering it virtually impossible for a particular power to comprehensively control human existence.

From this, it can be understood that the transition from the heterogeneous society of the Middle Ages to the modern Westphalian system, defined by the monopoly of violence, entailed a fundamental change in the nature of subjects within the system. In the mediaeval times, subjects were shaped by multiple, sometimes contradictory governance practices. This multiplicity created subjects with diverse aspects and logical inconsistencies, embracing various forms of rule. Such subjects, formed under this complex structure, found no place in the modern space, bound by the unity and fixed essence of the state. Conversely, in a heterogeneous society, subjects exhibit depth and variance in their existence, a result of the

multifaceted governance. Ruggie examines the social implications of one-point perspective, a technique introduced in the Renaissance era to emphasize visual unity and the singularity of the subject by portraying it from a fixed and singular viewpoint. This approach contrasted with traditional paintings and illustrations, which depicted subjects from various angles to highlight their symbolic meanings and social significance (1993).

The contradictory subject, which may seem puzzling from today's standpoint, is explicitly elucidated in the theological works of thinkers like Thomas Aquinas. Following Aristotle's traditional category theory, Aquinas views all finite beings as mirroring God's infinite existence through imitation. This relationship not only creates an order between God and created beings but also emphasises the imperfection of existence. For those beings imitating the perfection of God, understanding 'Being' is formed through analogy, an approach that compares two things in different ways, such as 'health' in complexion symbolising health in a man, and in diet representing the cause of that health (Aquinas, 1964, p.67). This attempt to understand God's Being through analogy, without logical necessity, brings about a mystifying dissimilarity alongside similarity. This leads to a simultaneous grasp of existence and Being with mystical depth, rendering a rational explanation for its cause unattainable (Pickstock, 1998). Such cognition forms the foundation for contradictions in the mediaeval subjects. By finite beings participating in the infinite, the subject becomes a distinct entity within its boundaries, yet also transcends those very boundaries, allowing for inherent contradictions. Unlike Hegel's approach to resolving contradictions through dialectics, mediaeval theology permits a higher harmony beyond logical opposition (Pickstock, 2005).

From the 13th to the 14th century, the arrival of John Duns Scotus' revolutionary idea of the "univocity of being" was profoundly significant. He directly challenged the traditional hierarchy of Christian theology that emphasised participation and imitation. Scotus's assertion in *Ordinatio* (1989) was that the concept of being is metaphysically superior to both the infinite and the finite. This break from tradition liberated existents from their internal connection with God, leading to a belief that individual beings are independent of their causes, existing self-sufficiently. This shift in perspective opened up new epistemological possibilities for understanding being previously considered unknowable. The focus of metaphysics shifted from God to existence, creating a new paradigm where existents could be understood as true within their own conditions, no longer bound by mystical

principles. Scotus's thinking can be seen as a precursor to Kant's epistemological advances, allowing modern philosophy to be characterised as Scotistic (Pickstock, 2005).

The ontological approach of Aquinas, which accepts contradictions, and the more consistent epistemological perspective introduced by Scotus, each correspond to the character of subjects in the Middle Ages and modern era respectively. Put simply, the international systems of the mediaeval and modern times differ in their governance structure, a distinction that can be further traced to the differing nature of the subjects that form the components of these systems.

3. Modern Political Space

3.1. The Transformation of the Subject

The concept of the subject, as understood in modern political philosophy's principles of sovereignty and statehood, contrasts sharply with the mediaeval subject, which could contain contradictions. Carl Schmitt, who characterised politics as the distinction between friend and enemy, is the primary exponent of this modern thought, embodying contemporary ontology. Schmitt asserts, 'In preparing for the extreme possibility of battle against a real enemy, the political entity is not only essential but also decisive for defining friends or enemies; it is sovereign in this context and not in any absolute sense. Without this, the political entity does not exist.' (2007, p.39). Such a declaration necessitates that friends are friends and enemies are enemies, and that each subject must be stable and retain its self-identity. Any contrary subject cannot be considered a political subject in modern terms.

Therefore, the establishment of sovereignty within political communities by distinguishing friends from enemies also signifies gaining sovereignty over one's self. This is achieved by addressing contradictions resulting from the self's internal diversity through relationships with friends and foes, leading to a well-defined, absolute existence. In modern philosophy, the self is confined within its boundaries, excluding plurality and oppressing the contradictory self as the enemies. The inauguration of the modern political landscape relies solely on the self's governance. The Westphalian system assumes the existence of states akin to billiard balls, and similarly, subjects that are also defined in such clear-cut terms.

Sanjuro Tomonaga, who introduced Kantian philosophy to Japan in the early 20th century, formulated a view of world formation based on "The Perpetual Peace: A Philosophical Sketch." According to him, autonomous individuals, through social contracts, constitute a state. These autonomous sovereign states, in turn, make up the international community. Shibasaki reorganizes this understanding of Kant's three stages leading to an incommensurable, mutually referential world formation, using the terms Self-State-International Relations (2009). In line with the main argument of this study, it can be proposed that existential unified subjects, sovereign states, and the Westphalian system coexist as three interdependent pillars shaping the modern global landscape.

On the other hand, when this framework is applied to medieval society, three corresponding stages emerge: subjects fraught with internal contradictions, states unable to exercise sovereignty, and a Heteronomous Society. When Reynolds contends that states were present in the Middle Ages, it must be critically examine the fact that 'sovereignty' wouldn't have been an apt term to describe their attributes. What does it mean to say that the mediaeval European system avoided uniformity, and that power and authority were diverse and intermingled? In a mediaeval heteronomous society, where subjects transcended themselves, ambiguity prevented the clear definition of sovereignty through identifying friends and foes, thus making the execution of power theoretically unfeasible. Mere control of violence, to a "more or less" degree, can never amount to sovereignty. Therefore, the distinctions between the mediaeval and modern periods in international relations extend beyond the differences in the international system itself, encompassing also the variances in the subjects making up that system. Sovereignty operates in a homogenous space defined by uniform subjects and the exclusive control of violence. On the other hand, the nature of the state in a complex space that assumes contradictory subjects and a lack of monopoly over violence is fundamentally different.

3.2. The Hidden Brutality

Schmitt's political ideas are widely linked to the current Westphalian system in international politics. Morgenthau valued Schmitt's contributions, which were founded in jurisprudence and emphasised the importance of politics. Both thinkers criticised liberalism, with Schmitt

specifically attributing the collapse of politics to the international order (Koskenniemi, 2001). They shared a common perspective, seeing the state as the only entity capable of forging political unity for the defence of modern society (Pichler, 1998). Moreover, Schmitt's influence extends to both neorealism and neoliberalism, with his ideas resonating strongly in these theories. Both approaches emphasise a structural view and reduce international relations to state interactions. The modern state, as envisioned at this time, is defined by sovereignty and encompasses both absolute power within and limitations without. The anarchy that emerges from this understanding serves as the foundation for both theoretical frameworks.

Inasmuch as the Westphalian system places sovereign states as its constituent elements, Schmitt's political concept is inseparably attached. The Westphalian system emerges as an international order with relative stability by a political community maintaining the principle of this modern state while simultaneously keeping a balance to coexist with other political communities in international society. Schmitt supports a minimal international law (*jus publicum Europaeum*) and order characterised by mutual recognition within and outside sovereign states (2003). As a result, the political philosophy of Schmitt is fundamentally linked to the principles of the Westphalian system.

He positions the structure of international society of this era, which existed without infringement from the late 16th to 19th centuries in Europe, as Europe's golden age. According to Schmitt, wars between sovereign states in this period became a "une guerre en forme (war in form)" unlike the pre-modern wars where all brutalities were justified by principles such as Christian belief (2003, p.141). He claims that this understanding limited warfare territorially and turned its form into something akin to a duel, recognizing the opponents as *personae publicae* (public persons). The enemy was not to be annihilated but politically recognized, and wars between organised states pushed away barbarism, advancing the rationalisation of war. Thus, to Schmitt, the Westphalian system is positioned as a system of romance and peace, mitigating the intensity of war by completely converting its form into a political one.

However, can the idea of rationalising IR and escaping from barbarism through the Westphalian system withstand historical validation? Modern conflicts, in terms of their frequency, scale, and casualties, disprove Schmitt's idealised notion of noble duelling. In the

Seven Years' War, casualties accounted for one-ninth of the Prussian population and two-thirds of all troops, and undeveloped logistics blurred the boundaries between civilians and soldiers through looting, ransom and rape (Teschke, 2011). In major European countries, about 60% of the time from the 16th to 17th centuries was spent on wars, and all aspects such as the intensity of wars, size of the army, breadth of the battlefield, frequency of battles, and human casualties were intensifying (Burkhardt & Wehler, 1997). Teschke points out that by idealising relations between European nations, Schmitt ignored the intensification of modern interstate wars, omitted considerations of massacres against Native Indians during the American continent's expansion, and created a depersonalised vacuum as mere expansion by Spain and Portugal (2011). In Schmitt's concrete order, as prominently manifested in territory and exclusive legal systems, one can discern the concealment of historical barbarity. Furthermore, Teschke implies that such characteristics rather bring to mind similarities with genocide of the Amerindians and Hitler's Eastern Lebensraum or the mass extermination of Jews.

In exploring the powerful exclusion underlying Schmitt's theory, it is necessary to reference Giorgio Agamben's argument (1998). Agamben extends Schmitt's concept of the 'state of exception,' identifying the sovereign principle that not only literally deprived the Jews of their legal rights in Nazi concentration camps but also manifests in contemporary forms such as Guantanamo prisoners and brain-dead patients, creating 'killable' bodies. The connection between the Nazis and Schmitt has often been highlighted, particularly regarding Schmitt's definition of the 'state of exception' as a key sovereign power. This idea was heavily dependent on Germany's situation, facing a domestic political crisis due to the Versailles Treaty.

For Schmitt, who believed that law was subordinate to politics, a sovereign facing such an emergency situation could legitimately suspend the law temporarily and declare a state of exception for self-preservation (Schmitt, 2005). While Schmitt considered the 'state of exception' as a specific period grasped in time, Agamben views it as a spatially enduring domain. According to Agamben, the 'state of exception' is positioned outside the legal order because it is designated as external by the legal order itself, meaning that it is paradoxically incorporated within the legal structure. This suggests the principle of community formation, where the internal political space is shaped by such external designation. By presenting this

paradoxical relationship, Agamben extends the concept of the political enemy in Schmitt's political thought. This is not a mere indication of the exterior but a preservation of the memory of exclusion at the origin of the political community, an exclusion enacted from within by the sovereign (Abe, 2009). In other words, the state of exception exists continuously as an adjacent space to shape our everyday political space.

Agamben repositions this existence suspended outside by the sovereign using the term 'homo sacer,' which appears in ancient Roman law. The term referred to individuals who have committed a crime and are excluded from secular legal. Stripped of human rights, homo sacer was in the same position as a wild beast; anyone could kill him with impunity, and his death was socially meaningless. As seen in the relationship between homo sacer and society, the state of exception indicates a space that coexists concurrently with the political community, continuing to produce those suspended and oppressed from the political sphere.

What makes Agamben's observation profound is that it does not limit the mass killings in Nazi concentration camps to a unique German experience. Instead, he situates this within the broader context of modern philosophy, exposing how the "state of exception" and the production of "killable bodies" are global phenomena. The mass killings by the Conquistadors in the Americas, forced labour, and the scale of modern warfare, as well as the mass killings in Nazi extermination camps, all render the victims homo sacer who have literally lost all human rights by being designated outside the political space. Reflecting on the difficulties in mediaeval Europe in making clear decisions between friend and enemy, one can understand that this powerful exclusionary political practice is grounded in the existence of a subject with existential unity, presupposed by modern political philosophy, and a sovereign state that monopolises violence through sole governance. To position the Westphalian system as a noble space for duels, as Schmitt did, is to conceal the barbaric power of exclusion that sovereignty brings. What is preserved under the Westphalian system are the exclusions carried out in the name of sovereignty and the norms that justify and perpetuate them.

4. The principle of inclusion

4.1. Mediaeval Confinement

Agamben scrutinizes the Nazi concentration camps for Jews, highlighting harsh aspects of modern political spaces. However, what was the nature of exclusion and isolation in medieval confinement facilities, where the line between friend and foe was often blurred?

A prominent example of such medieval containment centers is the lazar houses. Foucault characterizes these isolation facilities as important forms of societal division leading to exclusion. They served as the prototype for "The Great Confinement," aimed at isolating and managing madness from society (Foucault, 2001).

Leprosy, a skin disease that proliferated rapidly in Western Europe around the year 1100, was widespread enough that by 1228, King Louis VIII's will cited nearly 2,000 lazar houses in France alone (Risse, 1990, p. 181). This disease was often confused with various skin conditions like scales and scabs. Historical chronicles show that other ailments like the Black Death and smallpox were sometimes also referred to as leprosy (Mac Arthur, 1953).

However, this term primarily refers to what is now known as Hansen's disease, characterized by peripheral nerve damage that can lead to limb loss and significant facial deformities. Consequently, individuals with leprosy have faced long-standing social discrimination and prejudice. Early Christian theologians like Justin Martyr and Origen considered leprosy a physical manifestation of sin and divine punishment. During the medieval period, the disease wasn't just seen as a physical ailment but also as a form of spiritual ailment (Lewis, 1987).

Françoise Bériac (1988) argues that the cultural practice of isolating lepers dates back to ancient Europe. According to Bériac, these individuals were often segregated from their families and communities, and were the subjects of societal fear. In medieval times too. In various regulations, such as those from the diocese of Coutances, lazar houses of Lijeu (1256), and Chartres (1264), lepers were required to wear closed cloaks to make them easily distinguishable. Additionally, miniatures from the 9th to the 11th centuries frequently depict lepers with *crécelles*, noise-making devices, to warn others of their approach. Though not a universal Christian practice, variations in these exclusionary customs existed regionally. Bériac (1988) also cites the ceremony performed when lepers were admitted into lazar houses as one such instance. Some even employed mock burials as rites of separation, symbolizing the patient's social death. These rites underscored both a literal and

metaphorical departure from society, shifting the focus of the individual's remaining life towards spiritual pursuits.

Contrary to the long-standing view among historians that medieval attitudes toward leprosy were driven by superstition and cruelty, leading to unjust persecution and exclusion, there are several counterpoints as well. For instance, bishops often established facilities not for isolation but to offer treatment, medical care, and essential provisions. The instruments that lepers were required to carry served not to deter people from approaching them, but to help these voice-impaired individuals effectively attract alms (Brenner, 2010). In fact, leprosy houses operated primarily on donations and endowments, and able lepers frequently left these facilities to beg for alms in nearby towns in exchange for housing and food, and remaining ambulatory rather than confined (Risse, 1990, p.180). Consequently, leprosy houses were commonly situated near social hubs, featuring gates that faced public squares. In some instances, residences were even constructed opposite these facilities (Miller & Smith-Savage, 2006).

Certainly, as reflected in medieval hagiography, lepers have often been depicted as objects of public fear, serving as a central motif. This aligns with what Foucault and many historians have long argued: they were commonly understood as subjects for fear, disgust, and exclusion. Yet, within the same societal fabric, there have also been concerted efforts to acknowledge and include them. The significance of this fact cannot be overstated. What exists here is a contradiction and ambiguity in social attitudes toward lepers, represented by different practices of inclusion and exclusion within the same societal space. Elma Brenner contends that medieval Western Europe's approach to leprosy was intricate and often contradictory (2010). Such "semi-inclusive" practices (Geltner, 2011) underscore the nuanced interplay between exclusion and inclusion in medieval society, offering a stark contrast to modern politics.

The ambiguous stance leading to a particular order can be observed even within the feudal system of the Middle Ages, notably in the institution of vassalage. During the 12th century, England and France held neighbouring dominions in northern France. Specifically, the Norman Vexin, which controlled access from Normandy to Île-de-France and even Paris, held strategic importance for both nations. However, the nobles who owned this region served both France and England. By mediating the conflicts between the two countries, they were

able to prevent escalation of disputes. These landowning nobles embodied a contradiction: they were subjects of England in one respect, and subjects of France in another. In this social order, composed of such ambiguous and contradictory entities, a structure was established that brought stability through a complex network woven by dual or even multiple loyalties. Moreover, Both countries historically refrained from defining territorial domains in rigid terms, instead viewing their boundaries as symbolic markers. This system deterred or limited conflicts (Eickels, 2005). There was no sovereign present who could clearly declare an enemy. This intricate web of allegiances gradually disintegrated as sovereign power increased, leading from the late Middle Ages into an era of absolutism. During this transition, the essence and significance of national borders came to be emphasized.

In medieval society, the coexistence of various conflicting principles in the same space successfully created entities that were ambiguously both friend and enemy. This interplay of exclusion and inclusion resulted in semi-inclusive social practices. Unlike modern political spaces, these practices managed to avoid the clear-cut political decisions that Schmitt envisioned.

4.2. Structures that Bring Absolute Exclusion

This assertion should not be misconstrued as a romanticised claim that the Middle Ages were characterised solely by fraternal love and a utopian sense of peace. In fact, historical occurrences such as an incident in France in 1321 underscore a different reality. In this event, a groundless suspicion led to the belief that lepers had poisoned water sources, culminating in the nationwide mass execution of individuals with leprosy. What then prompted the emergence of such 'killable' bodies in a heteronomous mediaeval Europe? Malcolm Barber contends that the fundamental catalyst for this indictment, followed by a widespread panic, resided not so much in the Christian perception of leprosy as a symbol of impurity but rather in the great famine that plagued Northern Europe at the time, coupled with the consequent extreme social stress. This social crisis of the time reflected a tendency among people to seek scapegoats, leading to the expectation that conspirators plotting to overturn society would emerge (1981).

The uniqueness of a crisis such as a famine, as opposed to other political or religious concerns, lies in its pervasive impact, not merely affecting specific stakeholders but inevitably touching all strata of society equally. The sharing of a crisis translates into the sharing of an enemy. By collectively recognizing a common crisis among all members of society, the intertwined and contradictory state where a specific subject could be a friend under one governance practice and an enemy under another is resolved, giving rise to an exclusive society where the enemy is recognized solely as an enemy. In this situation, the contradictions existing within a heteronomous society were resolved, enabling the formation of temporary agreements to create a common enemy. In a society faced with such a rapidly forming crisis and agreement on whom to consider an enemy, even if there were remaining governance practices to include against exclusion, the resources to realise this would be overwhelmingly scarce compared to normal times. Thus, it can be concluded that what enabled such mass extermination was not the heteronomous society of the Middle Ages, but rather the homogeneous society of that era.

Therefore, it would be erroneous to depict the Middle Ages as a society imbued with fraternal love and peaceful coexistence. However, it's reasonable to assume that these heterogeneous societies possessed capabilities for deterring conflict and preventing the rise of a strong exclusion. This discussion had tended to emphasize a temporal dichotomy between the medieval and modern eras for the sake of convenience, especially since medieval Europe was a period characterized by such diverse spaces. The crux of the matter isn't about this time-based division but rather concerns the degree of contradictions present within societies. In medieval settings, these contradictions were commonly accepted and even manifested routinely, as epitomized in the theology of Aquinas. Conversely, under the Westphalian system, such contradictions were suppressed under the banner of sovereignty, ensuring a perpetually recreated unified order.

5. Conclusion

5.1. The Legitimacy and Chaos Dichotomy

The article examined the principle of exclusion in the Westphalian system by contrasting it with the heteronomous society, more diverse and representative of the Middle Ages. The

Westphalian system, consisting of the sovereign state having a monopoly on violence, shapes the modern subject as an integrated and consistent being. Conversely, the heteronomous society that characterises the mediaeval era is composed like a patchwork, created by overlapping and mutually penetrating governance practices. This is further marked by subjects that carry internal contradictions. By dismantling the rupture between the modern state system and the heteronomous society down to the level of the individual subjects, a form of practice emerges that positions the Westphalian system as embodying a Schmittian exclusion.

The greatest achievement of Agamben's exploration of sovereignty's exclusive function in modern politics lies in its refusal to simply attribute the Nazi mass extermination to ethical monsters like Hitler or Germany. Instead, it exposes this as part of the same system that pervades today's international society. Enzo Traverso (2021) highlights the rise of radical right-wing groups, such as the 'National Front' in the 2017 French presidential election, the 'Alternative for Germany' in that year's federal election, and Donald Trump's racially charged victory in the United States. These extremist right-wing groups share characteristics of populism and nationalism, constantly engaging in identity politics that question who belongs to the state and who doesn't, thereby creating divisions. Traverso positions this new phase as "post-fascism", making an essential appeal to represent the remnants of totalitarianism, once aimed to be historicized as a negative legacy, as realistic features in today's world. This powerful exclusionary force sweeping across the globe must not be understood merely as a mistake caused by some radical ideas within sovereign states. It should be seen as an inevitability brought about by the political space constructed by sovereign nations.

In Schmitt's interpretation, the legitimacy of the sovereign is confirmed as a necessity for overcoming a state of civil unrest. This notion parallels Hobbes' Leviathan, which justifies itself through the fear of chaotic natural states, characterized by a war of all against all (Naruse, 2018). The Westphalian system reinforces its normative importance by establishing a stark dichotomy between the state and chaos, promptly defining anything that transcends national boundaries as chaotic. As Richard Falk points out characteristics of modern international society, such as "increased central guidance, and increased roles for nonterritorial actors," we often observe features in today's society that hint at a reversion to medieval traits (1975). However when exploring the possibility of a 'Neo-Medieval Order'

characterized by overlapping authorities and intersecting loyalties in the future of international society, Hedley Bull of the English School dismissed the idea without substantial consideration. He argued that "there is no assurance that it would prove more orderly than the states system, rather than less", and further stated that "it would contain more ubiquitous and continuous violence and insecurity than does the modern states system" (2012, p.246) . This is rooted in Schmitt's concept of the political, which could only understand a situation where friends and enemies are unclear as a political crisis.

This also casts doubt on today's state-building project, which has unconditionally integrated with peacebuilding. Andreas Wimmer (2011) challenges the conventional approaches of IR realism and liberalism, which base their theories on the assumption of stable sovereign states. These approaches often focus on conflicts between states but overlook the reality that the formation of the state itself has been a source of conflict. He empirically revealed that conflicts tend to occur at the timing of nation-state construction, which has been a significant cause of contemporary world conflicts, by recording the inter-ethnic power relations in various countries after World War II and utilising the data of Ethnic Power Relations (EPR). In a nation-state, the birth of a nation representing ethnic composition simultaneously delineates people who cannot attain the status of nationals. Thus, a mechanism existed whereby the division between those who were given legitimacy and those who were excluded from it became apparent, triggering protests, rebellions and civil wars.

This study offers a critical perspective against this state-centric theories and policies. This forms a norm that permanently shapes and continues to rebuild this system for the future. Today, we encounter a paradox where the Westphalian system, although born from a specific time, solidifies its role as a foundational principle in ongoing international society through a realist view. Shibasaki criticises this trend in IR as 'building its objectives and domains' (2016), emphasising the need to reassess the Westphalian system. There is a danger in overemphasising the normative significance of the Westphalian order; it may recognize only political communities that conform to the system and portray others as chaotic. The Westphalian regime holds normative meaning both as an ontological framework in IR and as a guideline at the practical level, such as peace-building and foreign policy. However, this must be challenged by re-examining the structural exclusion it creates. Therefore, this study

emphasised the necessity of research and practice aimed at transcending the Westphalian paradigm. The heterogeneous society of the Middle Ages seems to hold potential as an alternative. Seen from the present, this seemingly chaotic system functioned more to deter violence than to incite it. On the other hand, as discussed in this paper, the process of resolving contradictions through sovereignty did not alleviate violence as an order structure; rather, it escalated it.

5.2. Beyond Friend and Enemy

Chantal Mouffe's engagement "with Schmitt against Schmitt" (2005) echoes Schmitt's view that political liberalism's turn to individualism merely sidesteps politics, ignoring the inherent principle of exclusion. Yet, Mouffe confronts the unavoidable nature of political friend-enemy relations and exclusion, actively seeking a path towards pluralism. She views Schmittian politics, with its potential for physical annihilation of the enemy, as a form of antagonism. She accepts this antagonistic aspect as a permanent feature, yet explores ways to soften the intensity of this mutual hostility by transforming 'enemy' into 'adversary,' and 'conflict' into 'struggle.'

Mouffe brings in ideas from Derrida's constitutive outside, folding into her philosophy the possibility for the subject's identity to change and introducing a post-structuralist understanding of the subject. This contrasts with the traditional view of a unified subject and unveils that the dichotomy between political friends and enemies spreads across various domains like religion, ethnicity, and economics. By viewing the friend-enemy distinction as merely a 'part' of reality, and by relativizing the rigid stance that defines identity, she paves the way for envisioning alternative political methods that can configure friends and enemies in diverse ways. This exploration seeks the potential for bridging the seemingly enduring and incommensurable divide between friends and enemies by offering different viewpoints. It creates an opportunity where an enemy may also be seen as a friend. By walking this path, one understands that democratic politics' challenge is to curb conflict by reshaping the definitions of friends and enemies. Mouffe's strategies to temper Schmitt's concept of conflict steer away from the modern political space and the conventional subject, moving

closer to the subject and heteronomous society of the Middle Ages, as discussed in this dissertation.

Mouffe's argument assumes the presence of the state, but when recognizing this form of subjectivity, the need to view the state as the main affiliation for the individual vanishes completely. Without even referring to Deleuze's notion of nomadism, a subject that inherently lacks unity seeks to break down the modern sovereign state striving for uniformity. Considering that Reynolds' use of 'state' in mediaeval times greatly differs from today's meaning, the democracy Mouffe envisions moves away from the modern sovereign state. It leans towards a return to the mediaeval or even aims to dismantle the Westphalian system itself.

The examination of heteronomous societies will encourage researchers to envisage a new international system that allows for the deconstruction of the Westphalian system and brings about inclusion. It would also provide a blueprint for reassessing existing issues and call for a reassessment of contemporary issues such as far-right policies and civil wars. The existence of non-state actors reveals the constraints of the sovereign state. It must be recognised not as a subset of states in need of correction, but rather as a positive indication of new political possibilities.

In this study, the focus was laid on comparing systems across various epochs, but there was no room to explore the forces that instigated those transformations. Scotus's notion of the univocity of existence, as examined in this paper, was indeed groundbreaking for its time. Yet, it should not be leaped to conclude that the move from ontology to epistemology necessarily led to shifts in the actual political structure. Conversely, we must also consider the possibility that the Copernican turn emerged as a result of changes in the political system. Hence, it becomes vital to rigorously investigate the reasons behind the founding of the Westphalian system and the establishment and subsequent dismantling of the heteronomous system in the Middle Ages, all from a standpoint critical of a realist comprehension. While the former topic garners much debate in IR, the latter remains a field that's been somewhat neglected. Additional empirical research is needed to further bolster this study's arguments, particularly by gathering a more diverse range of cases that examine exclusion by today's sovereign states and inclusion under Neo-medievalist features. Another

limitation of this study is that it did not touch on the economic aspects in society. To delve into these dynamic aspects will likely present a focal point for future research.

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